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Effect of Electrical Steel Punching on the Performance of Fractional-kW Electrical Machines

Abdolmajid Abedini Mohammadi, Sunny Zhang, Adrian-Cornel Pop, and Johan Gyselinck, *Member, IEEE*,

Abstract—The effect of electrical steel degradation due to punching on the performance of fractional-kW electrical machines in terms of torque and iron losses is investigated. The local degradation of the steel is considered in the BH curve and iron losses model by continuous variation of the magnetic properties as a function of the distance from the cut edges. The newly introduced parameters are identified by fitting the proposed relations for the BH curve and iron losses with measured values obtained via standard Epstein frame test. The position-dependent BH curve is incorporated into magnetostatic FE equations. Then, the performance of two different synchronous machines, i.e. with permanent magnets and reluctance rotor, is analyzed by means of FE simulations. Considering punching, the average torque decreases by 0.5-2 %, while the iron losses can undergo an increase of 30-40 %. Moreover, in order to check the validity of the model, the magnetic friction torque of two permanent-magnet motors, one with an annealed stator and the other one with a non-annealed stator, is measured and compared with calculated values based on the FE model.

Index Terms—BH-curve, electrical steel, fractional-kW electrical machines, iron losses, punching

MANUFACTURING process and technology of electrical machines can have significant effect on their performance [1]–[6]. During different stages of the production, the magnetic steel is exposed to mechanical and thermal residual stress which adversely affects its magnetic properties (MgPs), i.e. BH curve and iron losses [7]. These stages consist of cutting steel sheets into rotor and stator laminations by punching, spark erosion cutting, or laser cut [8]; building up the stator and rotor stacks by interlocking, welding, or compressing [9]; and fixing the stator inside the frame by compressing, shrinking, or mechanical fixtures. Cutting, particularly by punching or laser cut, has considerable contribution into the magnetic steel degradation compared to other stages [10]. Still, punching is a common cutting method in mass production of electrical machines due to its lower cost and higher speed.

Normally the effect of cutting, be punching or laser cut, is studied by measuring the MgPs of magnetic samples cut into strips or rings with different widths by standard methods, i.e. single sheet tester or Epstein frame [11]–[13]. Furthermore, the effect can be directly investigated by measuring the MgPs of the assembled core of the electromagnetic device, e.g. stator

of electrical machines, using dedicated methods and apparatus [14], [15].

While many studies have identified and quantified the steel degradation due to punching around the cut edge, its effect on the overall performance of the machines, e.g. torque and iron losses, is less known. The effect can be pronounced in the fractional-kW machines in which some machine dimensions, e.g. teeth and stator yoke, can be quite in the range of the region affected by punching [16], [17].

In order to further study the effect of punching, first of all, the local degradation of the steel MgPs should be considered. It means that the BH curve and iron losses of the steel need to be a function of not only the field intensity (or field density in the case of iron losses) but also the shortest distance from the cut edge. In order to consider the local deterioration due to punching, BH curve and iron losses model can be modified using position-dependent linear [12], exponential [18], [19] or polynomial [20] terms. Then the newly-introduced parameters for BH curve and iron losses can be identified based on the measured BH curves for magnetic samples as an inverse optimization problem [21].

Secondly, the new BH curve needs to be incorporated into the electromagnetic model, e.g. finite element (FE). In this regard, the iron region can be discretized into some sub-layers along the cut edges, then each single layer can be represented by appropriate BH curve depending on its distance from the cut edge [19]. In order to increase the model accuracy, the number of regions should be increased. However, this approach can be cumbersome, particularly for regions with complex geometry. Alternatively, the BH curve of each single element of mesh can alter based on its distance from the cut edge, which results in continuous material model [18], [22].

References [16], [17] study the increase of iron losses and reduction of torque due to punching in synchronous reluctance machines (SynRel) with different power rating ranging from fraction of to several kW. However, the models are based on homogeneous deterioration of MgPs around the cut edges. In [20] and [23], the effect of mechanical cutting on the performance of induction motors (IMs) is studied based on the continuous FE model. In [24], the impact of laser cutting on the increase of iron losses and decrease of torque in a permanent-magnet synchronous machine (PMSM) based on FE model is analyzed.

In this paper, firstly an improved approach for modeling of the punching impact on the torque and iron losses is proposed, where the BH curve and iron losses model are modified for considering the punching. In contrast to previous studies, the identification of position-dependent BH curve and

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iron loss model is treated as a single problem. The new BH curve is incorporated into FE equations implemented by open source software ONELAB. The permeability of the iron changes continuously based on the distant from the cut edges, which makes the modeling procedure more efficient and accurate, as contrary to using a single modified BH curve for the deteriorated region. The effect of punching on the performance of two fractional-kW motors, i.e. a PMSM and SynRel machine, is studied. To the best knowledge of the authors, punching effect on the overall performance of the PMSMs is not addressed in the literature. It is observed that punching can considerably increases the iron losses in the range of 30-40 %, while the average torque reduction is in the range of 0.5-2%. Moreover, in order to check the accuracy of the model, magnetic friction torque of two PMSMs with 10 poles and 12 teeth, one with an annealed stator and the other one with a non-annealed stator, are measured and compared with calculated values based on the FE model.

In the next section, the proposed model for punching is set forward and the procedure for identification of its parameters is detailed. In section III, the FE model considering punching is introduced and some simple case studies are presented. In section IV, the adverse effect of punching on the performance of a PMSM and a SynRel machine by means of FE simulations is discussed. The experimental measurements of magnetic friction torque are presented in section V. Finally the paper is concluded in the last section.

I. MODEL OF PUNCHING

The magnetic steel under study is M330-50A. In order to model the effect of punching on the MgPs of the steel, the BH curve and iron losses are measured using four types of strips (see Fig. 1). The total width of each strip is 30 mm. However, it can be composed of thinner sub-strips with widths 6, 7.5, 10, or 15 mm. The tests are conducted using five various combinations of the strips by means of standard Epstein frame. The type and number of strips in each test is reported in Table I. According to the IEC 60404-2 standard, there are 8 strips in total in each test, which half of them are cut in rolling direction and half in transverse direction (see Fig. 2). The measured BH curves and iron losses are shown in Fig. 3 and 4 as solid lines, respectively. It should be noted that the BH curves are measured up to 1.8 T and are linearly extrapolated using the last two measured points for higher flux densities.

Fig. 1. The 30mm-wide strips used in Epstein test with 5, 4, 3, 2, 1 sub-strips with width 6, 7.5, 10, 15, 30 mm, respectively (from down to up)

TABLE I
NUMBER AND WIDTH OF STRIPS USED IN EPSTEIN FRAME TEST (THE FIRST AND SECOND NUMBERS IN PARENTHESES SHOW THE NUMBER AND WIDTH OF THE SUB-STRIP, RESPECTIVELY)

test	# and width of strips	# of cut edges
1	4 × (2×15mm) + 4 × (3×10mm)	40
2	4 × (2×15mm) + 4 × (4×7.5mm)	48
3	4 × (2×15mm) + 4 × (5×6mm)	56
4	4 × (3×10mm) + 4 × (5×6mm)	64
5	4 × (4×7.5mm) + 4 × (5×6mm)	72

As far as punching is related, as it will be shown in section III, the material degradation at flux densities higher than the knee region diminishes, and therefore the extrapolation method does not directly affect the comparative study in this paper.

Considering the punching effect, the permeability of the material is represented as:

$$\mu(H, x) = \mu_{n-deg}(H) \left(1 - \frac{2}{\pi} \mu_p \exp\left(\frac{-x}{a_\mu}\right) \left(\arctan\left(\frac{H}{H_1}\right) - \arctan\left(\frac{H}{H_2}\right) \right) \right) \quad (1)$$

where x is the nearest distance from the cut edges, and H field intensity. μ_{n-deg} is the permeability of the non-degraded material, assumed to be equal to the permeability of standard 30mm-wide strips. The four parameters μ_p , H_1 , H_2 , and a_μ need to be determined. The exponential term in (1) is for considering the physical fact that the cutting effect should diminish while the distance from cut edge increases. Also, the other term with field intensity is for limiting the punching effect to the region of the BH curve around and beneath knee region (see Fig. 4).

With the Epstein frame test, the average value of the flux density and therefore average permeability in the strips can be measured. By ignoring the stray flux outside the strips, it can be assumed that H is a uniformly distributed field all over the strip according to Ampere's law [25]. It means that at given excitation, H in (1) is independent of position and constant. Therefore, the reduction in average permeability of the strip due to punching is calculated by integrating (1) over the width of strip as:

Fig. 2. Epstein frame used for the measurement of MgPs of the strips; the number and direction of strips in each side of the frame are shown on the picture

$$\Delta\mu(H) = \frac{2}{\pi}\mu_p \left(\arctan\left(\frac{H}{H_1}\right) - \arctan\left(\frac{H}{H_2}\right) \right) \left(\frac{1 - \exp\left(\frac{-2W}{a_\mu}\right)}{\frac{-2W}{a_\mu}} \right) \quad (2)$$

where W is the width of the strip.

The iron losses density based on IEM-modified formula [26] is computed as:

$$P(B, x) = k_{h0} \left(1 + k_p \exp\left(\frac{-x}{a_p}\right) \right) f B^{\alpha_0} + k_{e0} (1 + x_{10} B^{x_{20}}) f^2 B^2 \quad (3)$$

with

$$B = \mu(H, x)H \quad (4)$$

where f is the frequency of magnetic field variation. k_{h0} , α_0 , k_{e0} , x_{10} , and x_{20} are loss parameters calculated for strips with negligible cutting effect, i.e. 30mm-wide strips. k_p and a_p are for representing the effect of punching on iron losses.

The term $(1 + x_{10} B^{x_{20}})$ in eddy-current loss in (3) is for considering the increase of eddy currents due to saturation [26]. It is assumed that cutting does not affect the conductivity and therefore eddy current losses. Hence, the punching effect is just considered in the hysteresis loss term. Again, the exponential term is for limiting the loss increase to the region around cut edge. Moreover, when the excess loss are considered as a separate term in (3), its expression can be modified similar to the hysteresis term. It should be noted that the effect of inter-laminar eddy-current losses due to microscopic edge burrs created by punching in the cut edges due to plastic deformation [27] is not considered in this study.

Since the measured iron losses are averaged over the strip, the average iron losses need to be calculated as:

$$P_{\text{avg}}(H) = \frac{2}{W} \int_0^{\frac{W}{2}} P(x) dx \quad (5)$$

Obviously, (2) and (5) are valid for a single sub-strip with given width; and, therefore, they should be calculated for all sub-strips in each test separately and added up proportionally for considering their cumulative effect.

It should be noted that the increase in iron losses originates from two effects: firstly, due to altering of the magnetic properties of the material around the cut edge represented by considering hysteresis coefficient as a function of distance from cut edge; secondly, due to the concentration of flux density at the center of the strip due to the reduced permeability of the material around edge. Therefore, the effect of BH curve deterioration also reflects in the measured losses. Hence, the identification of BH curve and iron losses parameters should be treated as a single problem, as opposed to the case where they are identified separately. The fitting problem is defined as a least square optimization as follows:

Fig. 3. Iron losses at 50 Hz for tests 1 to 5 in Table I; solid lines are measured losses and the squares show fitted values

Fig. 4. BH curves at 50 Hz for tests 1 to 5 in Table I; solid lines are measured and the markers show fitted values

$$\min_{B_0, H_0, \alpha} \left(\sum_{n=1}^{N_{\text{test}}} \sum_{m=1}^{N_{\Delta\mu}} \left| \frac{\Delta\mu(H_{n,m}) - \Delta\mu_{\text{meas}}(H_{n,m})}{\Delta\mu_{\text{meas}}(H_{n,m})} \right|^2 + \sum_{n=1}^{N_{\text{test}}} \sum_{m=1}^{N_P} \left| \frac{P_{\text{avg}}(H_{n,m}) - P_{\text{meas}}(H_{n,m})}{P_{\text{meas}}(H_{n,m})} \right|^2 \right) \quad (6)$$

while

$$\max \left(\frac{2}{\pi} \mu_p \left(\arctan\left(\frac{H}{H_1}\right) - \arctan\left(\frac{H}{H_2}\right) \right) \right) < 1 \quad (7)$$

where N_{test} , $N_{\Delta\mu}$, and N_P are the number of tests, measured permeability and iron losses data, respectively. Subscript *meas* denotes measured values. The optimization problem is solved using *fmincon* function in MATLAB. Inequality (7) imposes positive permeability constraint. The fitted iron losses BH curve alongside the measured ones are shown in Fig. 3 and 4 with markers, respectively. Measurements were available just at a single frequency of 50 Hz (obviously, more measurements at more frequencies are favorable and improve the accuracy of the identified parameters). The computed coefficients in (1) and (3) are reported in Tables II and III.

It should be noted that the intensity of the steel degradation depends not only on cutting method and steel grade but

TABLE II
IRON LOSS PARAMETERS DEFINED IN (3)

k_{h0}	α_0	k_{e0}	x_{10}	x_{20}
0.027	1.76	5.3e-6	1.85	2.88

TABLE III
PUNCHING COEFFICIENTS DEFINED IN (1) AND (3)

μ_p	$H_1(A/m)$	$H_2(A/m)$	$a_\mu(mm)$	k_p	$a_p(mm)$
2.5	35.9	128.1	2	0.67	1.74

also punching tool condition, e.g. its sharpness and cutting clearance [28]. Therefore, the identified parameters can vary depending on the punching tool condition. Furthermore, although the effect of the BH curve variation on the iron losses is considered by simultaneous identification of the BH curve and iron losses parameters, the effect of iron losses variation on the BH curve is neglected. In other words, the coupling between BH curve and iron-losses is still one-way, as opposed to the two-way coupling. In this regard, the iron losses should be integrated in FE equations via a hysteresis (e.g. Preisach [29]) model rather than post-processing-based method.

II. INCORPORATING PUNCHING MODEL INTO FE

The FE model for a strip and single tooth considering the punching effect is presented in this section. Regarding material properties, the non-degraded BH curve alongside the punching-related parameters reported in Table III are the inputs of the model. All FE simulations are conducted using open-source software ONELAB [30]. The FE formulation based on magnetic vector potential using first-order elements is implemented. It means that flux density is element-wise constant.

If the distance from the cut edge is represented by a piece-wise linear function, then permeability and consequently field intensity will be also element-wise linear functions and therefore the BH curve of material changes continuously. In this case, the shortest distance of each node from the cut edge first needs to be calculated. As an alternative approach, each single element can be considered as a separate region with its own BH curve. In this case, there are as many BH curves as number of elements. Moreover, the shortest distance of the centroid of triangular elements from the cut edge need to be calculated for assigning proper BH curve to each element.

With sufficiently fine mesh, both approaches produce identical results. In this paper the first approach is adapted. Moreover, higher-order elements with coarser mesh can be used in order to make the simulation faster [18].

Considering punching effect, the BH curve is a local function of the distance to the cut edge and therefore the whole steel is not defined by a single BH curve. Moreover, the BH curves measured by means of Epstein frame are in fact the average BH curve of the strip. In order to verify the FE model implementation, the average BH curve for a strip with

Fig. 5. Average BH curve of 6mm-wide strip calculated using FE model and (2)

width 6 mm is obtained by the FE model and compared with the one calculated analytically using (2). For calculating the BH curve with FE model, the average B is imposed with proper boundary conditions on the two sides of the strips and the required H is calculated. As it can be seen in Fig. 5, excellent agreement between these two BH curves can be observed. The corresponding flux density distribution with imposed average flux density 1 T is shown in Fig. 6 (a). It can be observed how the flux density tends to concentrate in the middle of the strip due to reduced permeability around the cut edges. Moreover, the normalized specific iron losses of the strip with respect to the ideal case is shown in Fig. 6 (b). The dashed curve shows the iron losses with $k_p = 0$. In this case, just the effect of flux concentration on the iron-losses can be calculated. It can be seen how the flux concentration in lower imposed flux densities contributes to iron losses and highlights the importance of identification of BH curve and iron losses parameters as a single problem.

Additionally, the FE model for a single tooth considering punching effect is implemented. The FE mesh and the map of distance from the cut edges are shown in Fig. 7 (a) and (b), respectively. The reluctivity map with imposed flux density of 1 T in all elements is shown in Fig. 7 (c). The reluctivity decreases from its highest value in cut edges to its minimum at the center of tooth. The flux density maps with imposed flux density 0.5, 1, and 1.5 T in the tooth trunk are shown in Fig. 7 (d)-(f), respectively. With lower flux densities, i.e. 0.5 and 1 T, the flux concentration in the middle of tooth trunk and yoke due to punching effect is clear, while with imposed average flux density 1.5 T, the flux density distribution tends to be more uniform like the case without punching.

The CPU time per iteration for a single magnetostatic run with the tooth model is around 5 seconds on a PC with 4-core CPU with clock rate 1.9 GHz and 8 GB RAM. The FE consists of 4886 triangular first-order elements with 2582 nodes. Regarding the mesh density in the FE model of the single tooth and machine models in the next section, it is adjusted by comparison with the required mesh in the simple strip model in Fig. 6 for having a good agreement between the average BH curve calculated analytically and using FE model shown in Fig. 5. Moreover, since the required time of FE run is not the primary concern in this study, the authors have been a little generous with the FE mesh density.

Fig. 6. 6mm-wide strip; (a) flux density distribution with imposed average flux density 1 T, (b) normalized specific iron losses at 50 Hz with and without $k_p = 0$

Fig. 7. Single tooth model considering punching effect; (a) FE mesh, (b) map of the shortest distance from the cut edges, (c) reluctivity map with imposed flux 1 T in all elements, and map of flux density distribution with imposed average flux density (d) 0.5 T, (e) 1 T, (f) 1.5 T in the tooth trunk

III. PERFORMANCE ANALYSIS OF FRACTIONAL-KW MACHINES

In this section the performance of two machines, namely a PMSM and a SynRel, is analyzed based on the developed model in Section II using FE model. The PMSM is originally designed for the electric power-assisted steering system in cars [31], while the SynRel machine is derived from the PMSM by keeping the main dimensions, i.e. outer radius and axial length.

It is assumed that the stator and rotor of the machines are not annealed after stacking in order to remove the residual stress

Fig. 8. Cross-section of the PMSM; the coil direction is show with \pm sign

due to punching, which is normally the case in mass-produced low-power electrical motors due to cost consideration. Therefore, the obtained BH curve for the punched strips can be used for the magnetic core of the machine. Moreover, the effect of rotor and stator stacking and compressing, pressing the stator inside the frame, and interlocking of the laminations on the magnetic properties of the core is ignored. They can further deteriorate the magnetic properties of the magnetic core.

The voltage equations of the machines in synchronous reference frame are:

$$V_d = Ri_d + d\psi_d/dt - \omega_r\psi_q \quad (8)$$

$$V_q = Ri_q + d\psi_q/dt + \omega_r\psi_d \quad (9)$$

where R denotes the resistance, ω_r electrical synchronous speed, ψ flux linkage, and i currents. In terms of inductances, ψ_d and ψ_q are calculated as:

$$\psi_d = L_d i_d + \psi_{PM} \quad (10)$$

$$\psi_q = L_q i_q \quad (11)$$

where L_d and L_q are direct and quadrature inductances, respectively. ψ_{PM} is flux linkage due to magnets (with the SynRel machine, it is zero).

A. PMSM

The PMSM has 10-pole rotor and 12-slots stator with fractional-slot, tooth-wound winding. The cross-section of the machine is shown in Fig. 8. The parameters of the machine are reported in Table IV. It should be noted that the rated power is for short time duty operation class, as opposed to continuous operation. As it can be seen, the width or thickness of the stator dimensions and pole shoes are quite in the range of the cut-edge depth reported in Table III.

In Fig. 9, the flux-density distribution in the stator and rotor with and without punching effect at open-circuit condition is shown. It can be seen that in highly saturated parts, e.g. some teeth and pole shoes, the flux density distribution changes slightly compared to the case without punching effect, while in the less saturated parts, the difference is conspicuous. Moreover, when the punching effect is considered, the flux

TABLE IV
SPECIFICATIONS AND PARAMETERS OF PMSM AND SYNREL MACHINE

	PMSM	SynRel
peak power	800 W	600 W
DC bus voltage	12 V	24 V
number of turns per coil	8	8
peak current	110 Arms	110 Arms
magnet remnant field	1.35 T	NA
minimum air gap	0.5 mm	0.5 mm
PM thickness	3 mm	NA
stack length	57 mm	57 mm
outer dia. of stator	86.6 mm	92 mm
outer dia. of rotor	50 mm	50 mm
yoke width	4 mm	6 mm
tooth width	6.8 mm	2.48 mm
max pole shoes width	3 mm	NA
flux barrier width	NA	2.5 mm

Fig. 9. Flux density distribution at open-circuit condition (a) without punching effect (b) with punching effect, and (c) difference in flux density distribution due to punching

Fig. 10. Iron losses of PMSM in whole torque-speed plane (a) without and (b) with punching effect

penetrates more in rotor owing to the reduced permeability of surface around outer radius as well as magnet pockets.

In terms of global quantities, the iron losses in the stator for the whole torque-speed plane with and without punching effect are shown in Fig 10. i_d and i_q for each operating point are selected based on maximum torque per ampere (MTPA) and flux weakening given the maximum phase current and DC bus voltage limitations. Considerable increase in the iron losses in the range of 25-30% due to punching can be seen. At lower speeds, the increase in losses is dominated by the hysteresis term, which is directly affected by punching, while the eddy current term starts to contribute more into loss increase at higher speeds owing to flux concentration effect in the middle of teeth and yoke.

The contour map of average torque versus i_d and i_q with and without punching effect is shown in Fig. 11. Depending

Fig. 11. Contour map of PMSM average torque (in N.m) versus i_d and i_q

Fig. 12. PMSM torque over one period with $i_d = -37.3A$ and $i_q = 154.6A$

on the currents, the reduction of torque is between 0.5-1.5 %. Despite the noticeable distortion of flux density distribution, the effect of punching on the average torque is not big. It can be attributed to dominant effect of air-gap reluctance in the whole magnetic circuit of the machine compared to the iron parts. The torque over one period with $i_d = -37.5A$ and $i_q = 154.6A$ for the two cases is shown in Fig. 12 (the currents are selected based on MTPA strategy). It can be observed that punching mainly affects the average torque, while the waveform and torque ripple do not change noticeably. Similar trend for other current angles can be observed.

In Table V, L_d and L_q as well as Ψ_{PM} at open-circuit with and without punching effect are reported. Ψ_{PM} is calculated at open circuit condition, while Ψ_{PM-FZP} is obtained with $i_q = 110\sqrt{2} A$ and $i_d = -10\sqrt{2} A$ by means of frozen permeability method. L_d and L_q are calculated based on (10) and (11) using

Ψ_{PM-FZP} . It can be observed that Ψ_{PM} decreases slightly due to the punching, which is in accordance with the small reduction in torque.

B. SynRel Machine

The 4-pole SynRel machine has a single-layer distributed winding on the stator with three slots per pole and per phase. The machine parameters and dimensions are reported in Table IV alongside the ones of PMSM. The cross section is shown in Fig. 13 (a). Owing to the distributed winding and also rotor structure, some dimensions, i.e. tooth width and flux guides width, are quite in the range of cut-edge depth. In Fig 13 (b), (c), the flux density distribution with and without punching effect and $i_d = i_q = 25A$ are shown. The corresponding difference is shown in Fig 13 (d). Because of relatively small tooth width and flux guides width, the distortion in the flux density distribution in the core of the machine is not as big as with the PMSM machine. Moreover, the distortion tends to diminish at higher currents due to saturation.

The iron losses in the whole torque-speed plane with and without punching effect are shown in Fig. 14 (a) and (b), respectively. Again, the currents for each operation point is selected based on the MTPA strategy and flux weakening. Also, it is assumed that the DC bus voltage is doubled in order to reach similar maximum speed as the PMSM. An increase around 40 % in iron losses can be observed. With this topology, the teeth of the stator are much thinner compared to the PMSM, and subsequently the increase of the iron losses due to the punching is higher than the PMSM.

The contour map of the torque versus i_d and i_q with and without punching effect alongside the MTPA trajectory is shown in Fig. 15. For given i_d and i_q , the average torque can reduce up to 2%, which is slightly higher than the PMSM.

Fig. 13. SynRel machine over one pole; (a) cross-section and flux density distribution with $i_d = i_q = 25A$ and (b) without punching effect (c) with punching effect, and (d) difference of flux density distribution due to punching

Fig. 14. Iron losses of SynRel machine in whole torque-speed plane (a) without and (b) with punching effect

Fig. 15. Contour map of average torque (in N.m) of SynRel machine versus i_d and i_q

Because of the relatively small dimensions of the flux barriers and teeth, their flux density is high and above the knee region of the BH curve, where the effect of punching starts to diminish. Therefore, despite the special structure of the rotor with many cut edges, the effect of punching on the reluctance torque with considered motor is not considerable. Furthermore, the torque waveforms over one period with $i_d = 80 A$ and $i_q = 140.4 A$ are shown in Fig. 16. Again, it can be seen

TABLE V
ELECTRICAL PARAMETERS OF THE PMSM

	ψ_{PM}	ψ_{PM-FZP}	L_d	L_q
without punching	9.00 mV.s	8.65 mV.s	36.5 μ H	47.3 μ H
with punching	8.87 mV.s	8.56 mV.s	36.9 μ H	46.8 μ H

Fig. 16. SynRel machine torque over one period with $i_d = 80$ A and $i_q = 140.4$ A

that the punching mainly affects the average torque, while the torque ripple does not change.

Another important parameter in SynRel machine is saliency ratio (SaR), i.e. L_d/L_q . The contour maps of SaR with and without punching effect are shown in Fig. 17. The inductance are calculated using (10) and (11). Again, with given i_d and i_q currents, the SaR value decreases with punching effect, which is in accordance with the torque reduction.

IV. EXPERIMENTAL STUDY

In order to check the accuracy of the model, the magnetic friction torque (MgFT) of two mass-produced PMSMs with 12 teeth and 10 poles and similar dimensions as the PMSM in section IV and the same magnetic steel grade is measured by means of a torque transducer. The stator of the first machine is composed of non-annealed teeth, whereas in the second machine, the teeth are annealed in order to remove the adverse effect of punching on the MgPs.

MgFT is equal to the slope of the machines iron losses curve versus rotor speed at very low speed at open circuit, and it is proportional to the average hysteresis loss [32]. This parameter finds importance in electric-assisted power steering systems. It should be noted that the open-circuit torque at low speed is composed of a DC component caused by magnetic and mechanical friction torque and harmonics results from cogging torque and the bench with zero average torque. The mechanical friction torque of the machine is measured using a dummy rotor without magnets.

Fig. 17. Saliency ratio contour map of SynRel machine versus i_d and i_q

(a) non-annealed

(b) annealed

Fig. 18. Stator teeth; (a) non-annealed (b) annealed

The annealed and non-annealed teeth are shown in Fig. 18. The annealing temperature cycle is shown in Fig. 19. It should be mentioned that the temperatures and durations of different annealing stages are optimized in order to achieve maximum possible reduction in iron losses. The temperatures and time durations are company properties and cannot be reported. The optimum annealing temperature is found by observing the magnetic grain sizes around the cut edges by means of magnetic-optical microscopy. The optimal temperature is selected as the one after which negligible increase in grain sizes is observed. In Fig. 20, the picture of magnetic grains around the cut edges before and after annealing with optimum temperature is shown. It can be seen that magnetic grains after annealing are recovered and much bigger.

Since the MgFT is measured at low speed, the hysteresis loss is the dominant term, and therefore the effect of eddy currents in general and inter-laminar eddy currents in particular is negligible. Moreover, in order to avoid the effect of extra losses due to mechanical strain from the frame, the measurements are conducted on the bare stator. The tooth stack is build up by circular-shape interlocks, which further increases the iron losses. However, it is shown in [33] that the increase of iron-losses with circular-shape interlocks, as opposed to

Fig. 19. Annealing temperature cycle

Fig. 20. Picture of magnetic grains around the cut edge of a tooth taken by means of magnetic-optical microscopy; (a) non-annealed tooth, (b) annealed with optimum temperature

TABLE VI
MEASURED AND CALCULATED MAGNETIC FRICTION TORQUE WITH AND WITHOUT STATOR ANNEALING

	non-annealed	annealed	reduction
measured	1.80 N.cm	1.24 N.cm	32 %
calculated	1.84 N.cm	1.32 N.cm	28 %

rectangular-shape ones, is not considerable. Regarding the temperature effect on the measurements, because the magnetic friction torque measurements are carried out at open-circuit condition and low speed (30 rpm), the copper loss is absent and iron losses effect on the temperature increase is negligible and basically all measurements are done at room temperature.

In order to increase the accuracy of the calculated hysteresis loss, k_{h0} in (4) is calculated using the interpolation of the measured iron losses for 30mm-wide strips at 10 Hz, which is shown in Fig. 21. The measured and calculated MgFTs of the machines are reported in Table VI. The measured MgFT reduces by 32 % after annealing which corresponds to 32 % reduction in hysteresis loss. In comparison, the calculated MgFT without punching effect is 28 % lower than the case with punching. The higher reduction of the measured MgFT can be partly attributed to the removal of the stresses due to other manufacturing processes in addition to punching, i.e. interlocking of stator laminations and fixing of stator teeth by small welding joints. Regarding the difference between absolute value of the measured and calculated MgFTs, it can be because of the non-identical parameters of the punching tool used in the mass production of the teeth and the cutting tool used for preparing the samples in Section II.

Fig. 21. Iron losses measured for 30mm-wide strips at 10 Hz

V. CONCLUSION

A model for including the punching effect on the BH curve and iron losses based on continuous degradation of MgPs of the steel around the cut edges was proposed and the procedure for its identification was set forward. It was incorporated into magnetostatic FE equations. The performance of two fractional-kW machines considering the punching effect was investigated by means of the FE model. It was observed how punching can lead to flux concentration in yoke and teeth at flux densities around and lower than knee region of the BH curve. In terms of global quantities, a small reduction in the machine torque, up to 2% depending on the operating point, was observed. Considerable increase in the iron losses in range of 30-40 % was calculated. Magnetic friction torque of two PMSMs, with annealed and non-annealed stators, is measured and compared with calculated results obtained from the FE model, which showed relatively good agreement.

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